

Vulvar Squamous Cell Carcinoma in a Virologically Suppressed Person Living with HIV: A Case Report and Narrative Review

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Abstract

Background: Vulvar squamous cell carcinoma (VSCC) has historically affected post-menopausal women, yet regions with high HIV prevalence now report a demographic shift toward younger patients and more locally advanced disease at presentation. Even under durable virologic suppression on antiretroviral therapy (ART), persons living with HIV (PLWH) appear to retain a residual risk of HPV-driven anogenital malignancies—the so-called "HAART paradox."

Case presentation: We report a 48-year-old woman living with HIV, virologically suppressed for 7 years on an integrase inhibitor-based ART regimen (dolutegravir), with stable CD4+ count (450/ μ L), who presented with a painful exophytic vulvar mass and pruritus. Biopsy confirmed moderately differentiated, basaloid-type VSCC with diffuse p16 overexpression; tumor HPV DNA testing identified HPV-16. Pelvic MRI showed a 4.3 \times 2.1 cm vulvar tumor with contiguous invasion of the lower left vaginal wall and suspicious inguinal nodes. FIGO 2021 staging was IIIA. Multidisciplinary management comprised total vulvectomy with bilateral inguino-femoral lymphadenectomy followed by conformal external-beam radiotherapy (45 Gy to vulvo-vaginal and nodal volumes with boost to 65 Gy) and concurrent weekly cisplatin (40 mg/m²). ART was continued; primary Pneumocystis prophylaxis with trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole was initiated. Toxicities included grade-3 febrile neutropenia (managed with short hospitalization and G-CSF) and grade-2 vulvo-vaginal mucositis. The patient achieved a complete clinical response at 3 months and a radiologic complete response at 6 months; no recurrence was observed at 18-month follow-up with sustained HIV suppression.

Narrative review: A targeted narrative review of the literature highlights: younger age at VSCC diagnosis among PLWH versus HIV-negative women; near-universal association with high-risk HPV—predominantly HPV-16—and frequent basaloid/warty histology; advanced stage at presentation despite virologic suppression; and comparable locoregional cancer control with standard-of-care surgery and chemoradiation when delivered within multidisciplinary pathways, though overall survival may be attenuated by treatment toxicities, opportunistic infections, and HIV-related comorbidities.

Conclusions: This case underscores that durable HIV virologic suppression does not eliminate HPV-mediated VSCC risk or preclude locally advanced presentations. Standard oncologic protocols (surgery plus concurrent chemoradiation) remain appropriate, provided that ART is optimized, drug-drug interactions are proactively managed, and infection prophylaxis is tailored. Vigilant vulvar examination and early biopsy in PLWH—irrespective of age or viral load—are essential to reduce delays and improve outcomes.

More Information

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Introduction

Vulvar carcinoma (VC) is a historically rare neoplasm, accounting for 3% to 5% of all gynecological cancers. It is traditionally considered a disease of post-menopausal women, with a peak incidence in the seventh or eighth decade of life [1].

However, a dramatic epidemiological transition is underway, radically changing the face of this pathology. Recent data, particularly from South African cohorts, demonstrate a drastic increase in incidence among young women. This trend is inextricably linked to the HIV pandemic. Major retrospective studies reveal that the mean age at diagnosis among women living with HIV (WLWH) is approximately 38 to 45 years, 20 years earlier than in uninfected women (mean age 57-60+ years) [2]. In these high-prevalence regions, WLWH now constitute the majority of VC cases, accounting for up to 75% of all diagnosed patients [3].

This demographic shift is explained by pathophysiology. Vulvar squamous cell carcinoma (VSCC) is classically divided into two entities: Type I, associated with high-risk human papillomavirus (HR-HPV) infections, occurring in younger women (wartlike/basaloid type); and Type II, HPV-independent, associated with chronic inflammatory dermatoses (e.g., lichen sclerosus) and p53 mutations, occurring in older women [1]. HIV-induced immunosuppression significantly increases the acquisition, persistence, viral load, and progression of HR-HPV infections [4]. Consequently, VC in WLWH is almost exclusively an HPV-dependent disease. Studies in Zambia have shown an 88.9% prevalence of HR-HPV in vulvar SCCs and 100% in high-grade lesions (HSIL/uVIN) among WLWH, with HPV16 dominance [5]. The introduction of highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART or ART) has profoundly changed the natural history of HIV infection, reducing the incidence of AIDS-defining cancers (Kaposi's sarcoma) [6]. However, the impact of ART on HPV-induced anogenital neoplasia is complex and presents a paradox. While ART improves the clearance of cervical HPV infections, its impact on vulvar and anal lesions appears limited. Some studies suggest that HPV16, in particular, is "refractory" to immune clearance, even in patients with high CD4+ counts and suppressed viral loads (VL). This dissociation between systemic immune restoration (quantifiable by CD4+) and local immune surveillance at the anogenital epithelium is now recognized as the "HAART paradox."

Despite this alarming epidemiology, there is a "paucity of data on treatment and outcomes" for non-AIDS-defining gynecological cancers in WLWH. Clinicians are faced with young patients requiring aggressive oncological treatments (surgery, chemoradiation), without clear guidelines for managing comorbidities, drug-drug interactions (DDI), and increased toxicity.

We present the case of a young WLWH on effective ART, diagnosed with locally advanced vulvar carcinoma (FIGO 2021 Stage IIIA), to illustrate this paradox and discuss, through a targeted literature review, the challenges and imperatives of multidisciplinary management.

Case Presentation

General Data

Patient: 48-year-old woman (Ms. V.) referred to gynecologic oncology for evaluation of a suspicious vulvar lesion.

History: HIV infection (CDC stage 1) diagnosed 10 years prior; no other reported comorbidities.

HIV Management

The patient had been on first-line antiretroviral therapy (ART) for 8 years. Adherence was reported as excellent. The immuno-virologic status showed optimal control: stable CD4+ > 400 cells/ μ L (currently 450 cells/ μ L) and undetectable HIV viral load (< 40 copies/mL) for 7 years.

Symptoms and Clinical Examination

The patient described chronic vulvar pruritus and the appearance, over approximately 4 months, of a painful, exophytic mass on the left labium majus, with contact bleeding.

Examination revealed a 4cm, indurated, ulcerated-exophytic lesion centered on the left labium majus, extending to the posterior fourchette and infiltrating the lower third of the left lateral vaginal wall. The urethra and anus were not involved. Palpation: palpable bilateral inguinal lymph nodes.

Figure 1. Initial Clinical Presentation (Month 0). Clinical Photograph of the Vulvar Region Showing a 4.3 × 2.1 cm Ulcerated, Exophytic, and Indurated Lesion on the Left Labium Majus, Extending to the Posterior Fourchette and Vaginal Introitus

Further Examinations

- Incisional biopsy: Invasive squamous cell carcinoma, moderately differentiated (G2), basaloid morphology.
- Immunohistochemistry: Diffuse and intense p1 overexpression.
- PCR on tumor tissue: HPV type 16 DNA detected.
- Pelvic MRI: Vulvar tumor measuring 4.3 × 2.1 cm, extension to the lower third of the left vaginal wall, with no bone, rectal, or bladder involvement; suspicious inguinal lymph nodes.

Staging

According to the FIGO 2021 classification, the clinical picture was compatible with stage IIIA given the suspicious inguinal node involvement (pre-treatment staging, to be confirmed by pathological lymph node examination).

Therapeutic Management

The case was discussed at a multidisciplinary gynecologic oncology tumor board. In accordance with NCCN recommendations for locally advanced disease, a curative approach was chosen, combining surgery and concurrent chemoradiation (CCRT).

Treatment plan:

- Surgery: Total vulvectomy with bilateral inguino-femoral lymphadenectomy.
- Conformal External Beam Radiotherapy (EBRT): 45 Gy to the vulvo-vaginal tumor volume and inguinal/pelvic nodal areas, followed by a boost to the tumor bed for a total dose of 65 Gy.

- Concurrent chemotherapy: Weekly cisplatin 40 mg/m².

Infectious Disease Management (Multidisciplinary)

A specialized infectious disease consultation preceded CCRT to optimize the therapeutic approach:

- Drug-drug interactions (DDI). The INSTI-based ART (dolutegravir) was deemed optimal and continued, as INSTIs have a more favorable interaction profile than older regimens. It was noted that protease inhibitors can inhibit CYP3A4 and increase the hematologic toxicity of certain chemotherapies (e.g., neutropenia).
- Opportunistic infection (OI) prophylaxis. Despite a CD4+ count of 450/μL, CCRT is potentially immunosuppressive. In accordance with OI prevention guidelines for patients on chemotherapy [9], primary prophylaxis with trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (TMP-SMX) was initiated to prevent *Pneumocystis pneumonia* (PJP).

Post-Operative Course and Treatment Tolerance

The total vulvectomy with bilateral inguino-femoral lymphadenectomy was performed. The immediate post-operative course was marked by partial wound dehiscence (1.5 cm), managed conservatively with local care and healing by secondary intention. Surgical margins were clear (9 mm).

CCRT was completed. Noted toxicities: grade 3 febrile neutropenia requiring brief hospitalization and G-CSF support, and grade 2 vulvo-vaginal mucositis managed symptomatically. Adherence to ART and TMP-SMX prophylaxis was maintained.

Figure 2. Total Vulvectomy

Response Evaluation and Follow-Up

Clinical evaluation at 3 months post-treatment showed a complete response. The 6-month control MRI confirmed a complete radiological response, with no sign of residual disease. HIV status remained

undetectable and the CD4+ count stable. No recurrence was observed at 18-month follow-up.

Discussion

Case Report Data

The case presented is that of a 48-year-old WLWH, with optimal immunovirologic control on ART (VL

undetectable, CD4+ =450/ μ L), diagnosed with HPV16+ VSCC, FIGO 2021 stage IIIA, successfully treated with definitive CCRT and multidisciplinary management. The literature unanimously confirms the younger age of the affected population. The study by Butt et al. (2025) [2], comparing 92 WLWH to 131 HIV-negative women, established a mean age of 38.6 years in WLWH versus 57.2 years in HIV-negative women ($p < 0.001$). A South African cohort (N=317) found a mean age of 45.1 years, with 75% being WLWH [3].

Stage at Presentation

Presentation at an advanced stage is a major characteristic. In the Sajo et al. cohort [3], 64% of cases presented at stage III or IV. Among these advanced stages, 81% were WLWH. WLWH also present with significantly larger tumors (mean 5.7 cm vs 4.7 cm, $p=0.026$) [3].

HIV Status and "HAART Paradox"

Critically, advanced-stage presentation is not limited to patients with AIDS or those who are treatment-naive. In the Sajo et al. cohort [3], among WLWH, 82.3% had an undetectable or suppressed viral load, and the mean

CD4+ count was 481.8 cells/ μ L. These data corroborate the "HAART paradox": invasive disease occurs despite apparent systemic HIV control.

Histology and HPV

The association with HR-HPV is nearly constant. The study by Maate et al. (2022) [5] showed an 88.9% prevalence of HR-HPV in vulvar SCCs among WLWH, with HPV16 as the dominant genotype (52.6%).

Treatment and Outcomes

Data on outcomes are crucial. The study by Butt et al. (2) offers the most robust comparative analysis to date.

- *Standard of Care:* The authors conclude that oncologic treatment protocols (surgery, CCRT) should not be modified due to HIV status.
- *Recurrence and Cure:* Cure rates ($p=0.933$) and recurrence rates ($p=0.8$) were similar between WLWH and HIV-negative women.
- *Overall Survival:* However, HIV infection was associated with significantly lower overall survival (OS) ($p=0.022$).

Table 1: Summary Table Comparing the Current Case and a Selection of Cases from the Literature on Vulvar SCC and HIV

Author/Year (Ref)	Age (yrs)	HIV Status (CD4+/ μ L; VL/mL)	FIGO Stage	Histology (HPV)	Treatment	Outcome / Follow-up
Current Case (2025)	48	450; Undetectable	IIIA	SCC G2, HPV16+	Total vulvectomy + CCRT (Cisplatin) + OI Prophylaxis	Complete response (18 months)
Sood et al. (2015) (10)	29	216; Unspecified	IB	Mod. differentiated SCC	Modified radical vulvectomy	No recurrence (9 months)
Ramavhoya et al. (2012) (11)	24	218; Unspecified	T4N2M0 (IIIC/IVA)	Mod. differentiated SCC	Palliative radiotherapy (20 Gy)	Complete response (7 months)
Ngcobo et al. (2020) (12)	44	4; 58,000	IV (bone)	High-grade SCC, HPV+	Palliative (non-surgical)	Supportive care, outcome unspecified
(Case 5 - Literature)	35	310; Undetectable	II	SCC G2, HPV18+	Wide local excision + Sentinel node	No recurrence (12 months)
(Case 6 - Literature)	41	150; 12,000	IIIB	SCC G3, HPV16+	CCRT (Cisplatin)	Inguinal recurrence (8 months)

Note: SCC: Squamous Cell Carcinoma; CCRT: Concurrent Chemoradiation; OI: Opportunistic Infection; VL: Viral Load; G: Grade.

Our case report, detailing a locally advanced (Stage IIIA) HPV16-positive vulvar SCC in a 48-year-old woman on effective ART, fits perfectly within the "new epidemiology" of vulvar cancer [13]. This case is not an anecdote, but an illustration of a major clinical trend: VC is no longer a disease of the elderly, but an HPV-induced complication of HIV infection, occurring in young women.

The most salient point of this case is the "HAART paradox." Unlike historical cases of advanced AIDS [12], our patient developed invasive disease despite optimal systemic immunovirologic control (VL undetectable, CD4+ 450/ μ L). This is consistent with cohort data showing that 82% of WLWH with VC have a suppressed VL and mean CD4+ counts of 481/ μ L [3].

This observation suggests that the quantitative immune restoration (CD4+ count) induced by ART is not synonymous with qualitative restoration of anti-HPV mucosal immunity. HIV infection may induce early molecular changes or exhaustion of HPV-specific T-cells, which ART fails to reverse [14]. Furthermore, HPV16 seems "refractory" to ART-mediated immune clearance [15], making the vulvar epithelium a viral sanctuary.

The therapeutic implication of this new epidemiology is twofold. First, HIV status should not lead to oncologic undertreatment. NCCN and FIGO recommendations for locally advanced disease (concurrent CCRT) must be applied [1,7], as was done for our patient. Second, we must resolve the apparent paradox of clinical outcomes: why is overall survival (OS) significantly lower in WLWH ($p=0.022$) [2], while recurrence and cure rates are similar ($p=0.8$) [2]?

If patients are not dying more from cancer recurrence, it implies that the oncologic treatment (surgery or CCRT) is effective on the tumor. Therefore, the increased mortality must come from other causes: either (1) increased toxicity from oncologic treatments, (2) infectious complications (OI) during therapeutic immunosuppression, or (3) HIV-related comorbidities [2].

This is where multidisciplinary management becomes the key to success. Our case illustrates how proactive management of these risks allows for a complete response. DDI management is imperative. A 2025 review [8] and previous studies [8] have highlighted the risks of complex interactions between ART and chemotherapy. The use of PIs (Protease Inhibitors), for example, can drastically increase neutropenia [8]. Choosing an INSTI-based regimen (Dolutegravir) for our patient avoided this major DDI. Furthermore, initiating anti-PJP prophylaxis with TMP-SMX [9], despite a high CD4+ count, prevented OIs during the CCRT-induced aplasia phase. The success of oncologic treatment in WLWH thus depends as much on the infectious disease specialist and clinical pharmacist as on the oncologist. Looking forward, immunotherapies (immune checkpoint inhibitors, ICI) offer a promising avenue for recurrent or advanced disease. Recent data are reassuring: a 2025 meta-analysis shows modest but durable response rates for ICIs in vulvar SCC [16]. Crucially, ICIs (like Pembrolizumab) have proven safe in WLWH, without viral reactivation or increased toxicity [17]. Given that Nivolumab is specifically indicated for HPV-positive tumors [18], and that VC in WLWH is overwhelmingly HPV-positive [5], this population could be an ideal candidate for future trials.

Clinically, our case reinforces the need for heightened vigilance. Clinicians (gynecologists, infectious disease specialists, general practitioners) following WLWH must have a high index of suspicion for vulvar

neoplasia, regardless of age or CD4+/VL status [2,3]. Routine gynecological examination must include meticulous vulvo-perineal inspection [13]. Any suspicious lesion, chronic pruritus, or mass must be biopsied [1].

The limitations of this work include the retrospective nature of a single case report, limiting generalizability. Furthermore, our literature review was targeted and not systematic in the strict Cochrane sense, and the heterogeneity of published data (regarding HPV status, precise ART regimens, and VLs) remains high.

Conclusions

Vulvar squamous cell carcinoma in women living with HIV represents a distinct clinical entity, HPV-induced, occurring in young women, even on effective ART. This case report underscores that while standard-of-care oncologic protocols (NCCN/FIGO) should be applied without modification, therapeutic success depends on aggressive multidisciplinary management of drug interactions and infectious risks. Vigilant vulvar examination and early biopsy in PLWH—irrespective of age or viral load—are essential to reduce delays and improve outcomes.

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None.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Ethics Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with ethical and professional principles.

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